

THE MAIN DIRECTIONS OF CREATING NATIONAL ONLINE TRADING PLATFORMS IN THE COUNTRY.

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Abstract

This article provides information about the activities of marketplaces, the possibilities of their entry into the market of Uzbekistan, the main directions of creating national online trading platforms in the country, and the characteristics of marketplaces.

Keywords

electronic trade, international market, logistics infrastructure, electronic online platform, marketplace, messengers, offline.

Online sales means selling products or providing services over the Internet. Until today, the most popular form of online shopping was internet stores. Currently, bots in messengers are also taking an important place in this direction.

Recently, the share of e-commerce volume has been increasing rapidly worldwide. Opportunities for entrepreneurship in our country are creating a basis for bringing national products to the international market. In addition, there is a need to create online quiz platforms in the country. As a result, the demand for timely and safe delivery of products purchased over the Internet is increasing. For this, the service provider has the task of creating the necessary logistics infrastructure.

Taking this into account, on February 8, 2018, a Memorandum of Understanding was signed between the national postal operator of Uzbekistan and the Swiss company "ZOODEL" at Uzbekistan Post. Memorandum on increasing competitiveness in the field of entrepreneurship in Uzbekistan, penetration of entrepreneurs into international markets and "Silk Road" countries (China, Kyrgyzstan, Uzbekistan, Kazakhstan, Russian Federation, Armenia, Azerbaijan, Georgia, Turkey, Lebanon, (Afghanistan, Iran, Iraq, Pakistan) is of great importance in establishing trade cooperation.

According to the memorandum, in the first half of 2018, a new electronic online platform ZoodMall will be launched in Uzbekistan, and through it,

manufacturing companies and dealers will have the opportunity to sell their goods without intermediaries.

For this, products of national and international manufacturers are placed in special mobile applications;

Through ZoodMall, national products are sold on international trading platforms such as eBay, AliExpress, Lazada, Cdiscount. As a result, the products produced in Uzbekistan are brought to the attention of hundreds of millions of buyers worldwide every day.

According to S. Mukhamedaliyev, General Director of ZOODEL for CIS countries, more than 300 million international customers use the company's mobile application. This allows Uzbek entrepreneurs to easily enter foreign markets. In this process, the national postal operator of Uzbekistan undertakes the quality delivery of products.

The process of digitization of all sectors in Uzbekistan, the further acceleration of the increase of national online trading platforms in the state, society and business activities is also reflected in the development strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026.

In accordance with this development strategy, it can be seen that the following are the main goals of our country.

Goal 9:

- Development of the "Electronic Government" system, increasing the share of electronic government services to 100% and eliminating bureaucracy.
- Expanding the provision of public services through mobile applications.
- Introduction of the Mobile ID system for personal identification in the provision of public services.
- Reduction of bureaucratic processes based on establishment of information exchange between state bodies and private commercial organizations through the "Electronic Government" system interdepartmental integration platform.
- Implementation of the authorization and notification system that ensures the protection of personal data.
- Establishing the practice of issuing and replacing temporary documents confirming certain facts and offering composite state services to citizens without waiting for their appeal.
- Simplifying the provision of public services to the elderly and persons with disabilities, creating convenience for them.

- Optimizing administrative procedures and automating the management process by digitizing work in state bodies within the framework of the "Digital Office" project.
- Abolition of the practice of requiring documents confirming certain facts from citizens due to the implementation of the "Citizens' Digital Passport" project.
- Expanding the practice of providing public services to citizens of Uzbekistan abroad.
- Digitization of public services and transfer of 20% of them to the private sector.

The most popular services, applications and phones of Internet users of Uzbekistan ¹⁶

"Intarget.uz" company has released a special issue of internet statistics of Uzbekistan as part of cooperation with "National Marketing Center" association. It showed how many users are on social networks, top lists of the most popular mobile applications and other important information.

In the list of 10 most popular sites of Uznet, according to the interpretation of the National Search System (www.uz), as of January 15, 2022, the news site www.kun.uz is leading, with 1,267 thousand visits per day. Another news site www.daryo.uz took the second place, and the sports news site www.stadion.uz took the third place.

¹⁶ <https://www.xabar.uz/uz/tahlil/ozbekiston-internet-foydalanuvchilarining-eng-ommaviy>

In 2022, the world's population will exceed 8 billion. Today, this figure is 8.1 billion. And now 68 percent of those people, or 5.44 billion, use mobile phones. This is a 3% increase from last year and means that 168 million new users were added in the last 12 months. This data was prepared by DataReportal and is compiled as of January 2023.¹⁷

It is known that the number of Internet users worldwide increased by 1.9 percent last year, and their number today is 5.16 billion.

If we divide Internet users by gender, we can see that 67.2 percent of the world's men use the Internet, and 61.6 percent of the world's women use the Internet, which means that more men access the Internet than women.

Similarly, when we divide the number of people who access the Internet from smartphones and computers, we can see that the number of people who access the Internet through a mobile device is significantly higher with 92.3/65.6 percent.

¹⁷ <https://www.terabayt.uz/uz/post/internet-2023-yilda-statiska-va-raqamlar>

ICT Minister Sherzod Shermatov announced that the number of Internet users in Uzbekistan has exceeded 31 million. 29.5 million of them connect to the network through mobile internet. The minister also noted that the speed of connection to the international Internet channel has increased by 2.6 times in the last two years, reaching 3200 Gbit/s.¹⁸

Google is the most popular search engine in Uzbekistan. 76% of Internet users use its services, and 19% use Yandex.

In conclusion, it can be said that there are the following main features of using online platforms in business activities:

¹⁸ <https://www.terabayt.uz/uz/post/internet-2023-yilda-statiska-va-raqamlar>

The above are the main features of online sales. Also, if you don't have an offline store, opening it online will greatly reduce the risk. Because little money is spent on opening and running a store on the Internet.¹⁹

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¹⁹ <https://kun.uz/uz/news/2016/12/27/uzbekistonda-onlajn-savdo-va-uning-aamiatl>

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